

ASSESSING THE ADDED VALUE OF ROBOTIC SOLUTIONS FOR THE TARGET OF ELDERLY INDIVIDUALS WITH A LOSS OF AUTONOMY THROUGH COCREATION

Abstract

In line with the successful aging models, a preliminary qualitative study with phenomenological interviews was implemented with 40 elderly individuals and caregivers. Complementary results from 8 cocreation meetings allowed us to prioritize the robotic functionalities to be improved and determine the real added value of robots in comparison with those of other IT solutions.

Many countries currently face the challenge of an aging population. The latter implies providing care to a growing number of elderly individuals whose health tends to decrease over time (Coughlin, Pope, and Leedle, 2006). At the same time, developing new solutions to help elderly individuals on a daily basis becomes imperative.

Within this context, technical innovations are promising and can help better monitor elderly individuals in their everyday life or remotely assist these individuals. Robotic solutions can help fill the gap between the growing needs in healthcare and services that occidental countries can provide today. However, this target has been misunderstood both in terms of the needs to meet through technological innovations and in terms of the environment (stakeholders and living areas) within which these innovations are implemented (Caic et al., 2018).

The goal of this paper is to understand the perceived benefits of robotic solutions by the elderly individuals with a loss of autonomy who wish to age well.

The well-being of elderly individuals and their networks of caregivers can be enhanced by companion robots. These robots, by having an impact on the life quality of an elderly individual, can diminish their feelings of loneliness and isolation (Augusto et al., 2012). Nevertheless, some elderly individuals and their caregivers seem to be reluctant to adopt robotic solutions (Broadbent et al., 2009), which is a key challenge to overcome (Caic, 2018). More generally, all of the identified divergences in the literature have assumed needs that are largely not being satisfied by today's robotic solutions.

Our research lies within the successful ageing model of Baltes and Baltes (1990): successful ageing stems from the implementation of effective aging adjustment strategies where the individual optimizes and compensates for the losses and gains associated with aging (the SOC model, Baltes and Baltes, 1990).

To question how more specifically robotic solutions can contribute to the well-being of elderly individuals with a loss of autonomy, we used the concept of Desired Aging Well which refers to the psychological, physical, social and financial objectives of aging well (Sengès, Guiot and Chandon, 2018).

In this perspective, we implemented our study within the European research project Agile CoCreation of Robots for Aging (ACCRA). By placing users (dependent elderly individuals and caregivers) at the center of the innovation process, this project was aimed at conceiving robotic solutions and service offerings that could respond efficiently to the needs, expectations and uses of dependent elderly individuals and their caregivers.

The methodology adopted in this project consisted of 2 main steps: needs analysis and cocreation. The needs analysis consisted of a cross-cultural study in France and the Netherlands and used a robot named *Buddy*, which was under development and had been made available by a robot developing company.

Phenomenological interviews were held in the Netherlands and in France to determine the needs. Two types of people were selected. On one side, elderly individuals between 65 and 91 years old, and on the other side, professional and informal caregivers were selected. Forty face to face semi-structured interviews were conducted. The recorded interviews were fully transcribed and analyzed with a thematic content analysis.

The purpose of the cocreation phase (2nd step) was to develop robotics solutions in close collaboration with the end users and caregivers. We followed the cocreation for

use/cocreation for other approach guidelines (Humphreys and Grayson, 2008) that we adapted to elderly individuals.

Eight cocreation meetings were held, each involving 8 elderly people and 4 professional caregivers (N =12), 2 researchers, a care organization manager and 4 robot developers.

During the cocreation sessions, demonstrations on 6 applications were conducted: companion, emergency, advice and reminders, remote communication, well-being, and entertainment. The participants in the cocreation sessions were asked to state whether they would use the application and which improvements should be implemented.

Each cocreation session was recorded with camera recorders and fully transcribed.

The analysis through the prism of the SOC model (Baltes and Baltes, 1990) highlights how robotic solutions can contribute to a better adjustment to the adverse effects of ageing: the results underline that the robot's functions are primarily part of a compensation strategy¹ and, secondarily, part of an optimization strategy².

As shown by the needs analysis and the resulting priority services (Table 1), the companionship functions through several interaction possibilities (verbal and emotional exchanges, games, and movements), communication possibilities (audio and video calls, and sharing of photos and videos), and well-being possibilities (coaching to help regulate emotional states and to conduct physical activities) constituted the main robotic benefits in comparison with the security functions already assumed by today's teleassistance devices. With regards to the security aspect, a robot seemed to be complementary to traditional teleassistance solutions, in comparison to which the robot had many advantages to help the elderly individuals to age well.

Insert Table 1 about here

The cocreation approach made it possible to guide the technological development of the robot. As a prototype would be tested later during the experimentation phase among elderly individuals at home and at senior residences, this research constituted the first step in the development of solutions through the evolution of a robot and services that could be used to help elderly individuals to age well. In comparison with other devices such as teleassistance products or tablets, the companionship, communication, well-being and entertainment functions of associated services were rated as more important. Hence, as one of the participants stated during the final cocreation meeting: "*Buddy* helps us to age well" (Serge, 82 years old). This illustrates how the robot whose physical presence allows the deployment of adjustment strategies (optimization and compensation) and to achieve all or part of the goals associated with the Desired Aging Well concept. In particular, this research, by highlighting the importance of affective goals to optimize social resources and compensate for

¹ As people grow older, they are faced with the loss or decline of some of their abilities and resources (temporarily or permanently). Compensation consists of using alternative means to attain the objectives selected when the initial means are no longer available or effective (Freund and Baltes, 2002)

² Optimization involves developing means in relation to goals (Freund and Baltes, 2002). It consists of acquiring, allocating, maintaining or improving the means and resources needed to attain the objectives selected while aging.

loneliness, reveals a complementary facet of the social dimension of the Desired Aging Well concept that was not taken into account before (Sengès and al., 2018).

This results in essential functionalities of the robot to be implemented to promote its adoption with a view to successful aging (Baltes and Baltes, 1990). In this perspective, our research argued in favor of the implementation of a geron-robot-servuction approach, marketing services management approach to be designed for the use of robots by elderly individuals with a loss of autonomy who wish to age well.

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Table 1. Priority services: service recommendations based on the user needs

USERS	PRIORITY SERVICES (<i>Service recommendations based on the end-user needs</i>)		
E=Elderly individual F=Formal caregiver I=Informal caregiver	Ranking	Needs	Robotic services
EFI F EFI EFI (NL) F (Fr)	1 Very high priority 1 Very high priority 2 High priority 3 Medium priority	1. SAFETY NEEDS 1.1 Risk of falls 1.2 Warning a caregiver 1.3 Forgetting to drink 1.4 Forgetting medications and appointments 1.5 Monitoring the environments of elderly individuals for safety (turn off gas, close doors, etc.)	PROTECTION ROBOT a) Detecting and preventing falls, and warning a caregiver b) Reminding to drink c) Helping with medications and medical appointments d) Monitoring elderly individuals in their environments
EFI	1 Very high priority	2. COMPANIONSHIP NEEDS 2.1 Loneliness / isolation 2.2 Need for companionship	COMPANION ROBOT Endearing and playful companion that is a daily presence. Interactions between the robot and the user (verbal and physical).
EFI	2 High priority	3. COMMUNICATION NEEDS 3.1 Difficulties with the phone 3.2 Difficulties with IT communication tools (Skype...) 3.3 Long distance from relatives	COMMUNICATION ROBOT a) Phone call b) Video call c) Sharing of media on the robot's screen: photos, drawings and videos.
EFI <i>(controversial for F)</i>	2 High priority	4. WELL-BEING NEEDS 4.1 Maintains a suitable well-being level 4.2 Often anxious or stressed 4.3 Serious health concerns 4.4 Difficulties with sleeping 4.5 Heart rate problems	BENEFIT ROBOT a) Zen activity coach: calming exercises. b) Health and mood status: fun tests to measure the health state and mood; the robot can also warn a caregiver. c) Physical activity coaching.
EFI EFI EF	2 High priority 2 High priority 4 Low priority	5. ENTERTAINMENT NEEDS 5.1 Needs to be entertained 5.2 Difficulties with reading (poor vision) 5.3 Needs to learn new things	ENTERTAINMENT ROBOT a) Games: alone or in conjunction with the network of an elderly individual; cognition games to maintain the memory. b) Reading: books and newspapers. c) Learning: foreign languages, songs, poetry, etc.
EF <i>(controversial for F)</i>	4 Low priority	6. MEAL NEEDS	MEAL COACH Menu ideas and nutritional advice.

NL = Netherlands; Fr= France